

SICF/SiC STIFFNESS PREDICTION, THERMAL RESIDUAL STRESS AND PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE SIMULATION BY MICRO-MECHANICS MODEL

Bin LIU ICCM22-I/717

School of Aeronautics, Northwestern Polytechnical University, Xi'an, China

Mechanism Introduction

- Focusing on predicting the macro-stiffness and thermal residual stress for SiCf/SiC composites, 3D micro-structure finite element analysis methods are applied to representative volume elements and the calculation.

Cuboid RVE including corresponding surfaces, edges and points

SiCf/SiC RVE geometry and finite element mesh

3D RVE micro-model

Calculating and Predicting Results

Comparison and Conclusion

- Basing on RVE ideology with PBC, a 3D micro-structure FEA methodology is effective to calculate the equivalent stiffness for CMCs.
- Homogeneous variation of interphase Young's modulus is investigated for considering the effect of interphase elastic modulus on TRS during material design stage.
- The effect of interphase thickness on TRS is investigated by rebuilding the model.